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Integrating neuromarketing into brand trust building strategies in the digital environment

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Abstract. The relevance of studying the theoretical and applied aspects of neuromarketing tools in brand promotion stems from the rapid digitalization of business processes, the growing importance of the emotional factor in consumer decision-making, and the diminishing effectiveness of traditional marketing approaches. The **purpose of the article** is to explore ways to integrate neuromarketing technologies into the strategy for building trust in brands in the digital environment and to formulate practical recommendations for their effective implementation in the activities of enterprises. **Methods.** The research methodology is based on an interdisciplinary approach that combines economic analysis, content analysis of modern neuromarketing methods, and a comparative review of domestic and foreign developments. **Results.** During the research process, it was established that up to 95% of consumer decisions are made subconsciously; therefore, neuromarketing provides unique opportunities for accurately identifying unconscious motives and predicting reactions to brand stimuli. Key neurotechnologies are systematized, and their ability to form an emotional response,

which is the basis of consumer trust and loyalty, is shown. The practices of personalization, omnichannel interaction, content visualization, and emotional storytelling, which enhance the effect of neuromarketing approaches, were analyzed. It was found that the combination of emotional engagement with conscious cognitive confirmations of brand reliability ensures long-term customer loyalty. Based on international experience and Ukrainian market characteristics, a set of recommendations was developed that covers ethical standards for working with neurodata, developing the competencies of marketing teams, and implementing personalization and analytics to measure the level of consumer trust in the brand.

Conclusions. The scientific novelty of the study lies in substantiating a comprehensive approach to integrating neuroanalytics, digital communications, and ethical principles into brand strategy. The practical significance lies in the application of the developed recommendations by enterprises in various industries to create long-term relationships with consumers, increase competitiveness, and promptly identify risks of loss of trust. The proposed approach can also serve as the basis for further research into the quantitative measurement of trust levels and the development of operational neuroanalytic tools.

Keywords: neurotechnology, consumer trust, digital communications, brand reputation, marketing personalization.

Інтеграція нейромаркетингу у стратегії побудови довіри до брендів у цифровому середовищі

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Анотація. Актуальність дослідження теоретичних та прикладних аспектів застосування інструментів нейромаркетингу в просуванні брендів зумовлена стрімкою цифровізацією бізнес-процесів, зростанням ролі емоційного чинника у споживчому виборі та зниженням ефективності традиційних маркетингових підходів. **Мета** статті – дослідити шляхи інтеграції нейромаркетингових технологій у стратегії формування довіри до брендів у цифровому середовищі та сформулювати практичні рекомендації для їх ефективного впровадження в діяльність підприємств. **Методи.** Методологія дослідження спирається на міждисциплінарний підхід, що поєднує економічний аналіз, контент-аналіз сучасних методів нейромаркетингу, а також порівняльний огляд вітчизняних та зарубіжних напрацювань. **Результати.** У процесі дослідження встановлено, що до 95% рішень споживачів ухвалюються підсвідомо, тому нейромаркетинг забезпечує унікальні можливості для точного виявлення несвідомих мотивів і прогнозування реакцій на брендові стимули. Систематизовано ключові нейротехнології та показано їхню здатність формувати емоційний відгук, що є основою довіри та лояльності споживачів. Проаналізовано практики персоналізації, омніканальної взаємодії, візуалізації контенту й емоційного сторітелінгу, які посилюють ефект нейромаркетингових підходів. Виявлено, що саме поєднання емоційного залучення зі свідомими когнітивними підтвердженнями надійності бренду забезпечує тривалу лояльність клієнтів. На підставі міжнародного досвіду й українських ринкових особливостей розроблено комплекс рекомендацій, що охоплюють етичні стандарти роботи з нейроданими, розвиток компетенцій маркетингових команд, впровадження персоналізації та аналітики для вимірювання рівня довіри споживачів до бренду. **Висновки.** Наукова новизна дослідження полягає в обґрунтуванні комплексного підходу до інтеграції нейроаналітики, цифрових комунікацій та етичних принципів у стратегії брендів. Практична значущість полягає в можливості застосування розроблених рекомендацій підприємствами різних

галузей для створення довгострокових відносин зі споживачами, підвищення конкурентоспроможності та своєчасного виявлення ризиків втрати довіри. Запропонований підхід також може стати підґрунтям для подальших досліджень кількісного вимірювання рівня довіри та розроблення інструментів оперативної нейроаналітики.

Ключові слова: нейротехнології, споживча довіра, цифрові комунікації, брендова репутація, персоналізація маркетингу.

Problem statement. The active digitalization of business and increased competition in the online environment are transforming the mechanisms of interaction between brands and consumers. Traditional marketing tools are gradually losing their effectiveness, as users are overloaded with information, and trust in advertising is decreasing. In these conditions, companies are forced to look for new ways to form an emotional connection with consumers to ensure long-term loyalty. Neuromarketing, which combines knowledge about the brain with modern communication technologies, is a key tool for understanding the hidden motives of buyer behavior and predicting their reactions to the brand [1, p. 84-85].

The problem is that the integration of neuromarketing methods into trust-building strategies lacks established approaches. Most companies employ separate techniques without integrating them into a systematic brand reputation management strategy. At the same time, world experience shows that the combination of biometric measurements, emotion analysis and digital analytics can significantly increase the level of audience engagement and form stable trusting relationships [2, p. 10-12; 3; 4, p. 574-575].

The complexity of the problem is exacerbated by the rapid development of digital communication channels and social networks, where brands must maintain a constant dialogue with consumers. The effectiveness of such interaction depends on the ability to take into account emotional triggers that trigger trust mechanisms and risk perception. Insufficient scientific and practical development of integrated

strategies that combine neuromarketing and trust management creates the risk of fragmentation of management approaches and communications and, as a result, loss of competitive advantages.

Therefore, research into integrating neuromarketing into strategies for building trust in brands within the digital environment is a timely and socially significant task. It aims to deepen the theoretical foundations and develop practical recommendations for businesses on forming stable, trusting relationships with consumers in a dynamic digital economy.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Recent years have been marked by the active development of neuromarketing research, which combines economic theories with neuroscience methods. Ukrainian authors, in particular O. Bratko and N. Burda, trace the evolution of content marketing, emphasizing its transition to emotionally oriented formats that create the prerequisites for trust in the brand [5]. This opinion is supported by A. Danyliuk, who reveals the epistemological principles of using neuromarketing technologies in the formation of a brand strategy, emphasizing the need for deeper consideration of consumers cognitive reactions [6]. At the same time, I. Momotkov emphasizes a new vision of customer behavior, thanks to biometric methods that allow for the identification of unconscious factors in the choice of goods [1].

In a global context, K. Shahzad and co-authors describe the influence of emotions and personality traits on digital purchasing behavior based on thematic analysis [4]. H. Kemora and co-authors generalization of international experience indicates the growing effectiveness of neuromarketing in digital marketing and offers a systematic review of applied approaches [7]. K. Singh and co-authors describe the transformation of neuromarketing approaches in the post-pandemic world, emphasizing the need to build long-term trust [8]. V. Nazarenkos study highlights the evolution of the use of makeup as a tool of visual identity in the mass media, which may serve as additional evidence of the importance of the visual image of a brand for building trust [9]. Taken together, these works outline the primary

mechanisms by which the emotional component influences the building of trusting relationships, but leave open the question of integrating such approaches into a sustainable brand management strategy.

The digital dimension of the problem is explored by K. Kupriienko, M. Ungurian, and A. Kyryliuk, who analyze social networks as a leading channel of brand interaction [10]. A similar vector is considered by T. Ryabovolik and N. Pitel, emphasizing the importance of combining innovations and digital communications in retail enterprises [11]. In the field of content, the results of O. Yashchenko on overcoming information overload and building trust through the relevance of messages are essential [12]. D. Verzhykovskyi research demonstrates that augmented reality is becoming a promising tool for deepening the emotional experience of interaction with a brand [13]. Although these works convincingly demonstrate the value of digital channels for communication, they do not sufficiently reveal the combination of digital formats with neurometric measurement methods and trust management.

A separate direction is research on the individualization of marketing strategies. O. Katunina demonstrates the possibilities of integrating artificial intelligence models to build consumer behavioral profiles, which increases the personalization of communication [14]. O. Rybak analyzes innovative approaches to marketing management in the context of digital transformation, focusing on new demand forecasting tools [15]. In turn, O. Rashevchenko demonstrates that emotional marketing can form unique competitive advantages; however, the author pays less attention to the neurophysiological foundations of this process [16]. These conclusions outline the prospects of combining artificial intelligence with neuromarketing, but confirm the need for further interdisciplinary justification.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the general problem. Existing research provides rich material for understanding neuro-oriented marketing, including its theoretical foundations, neuro-measurement tools, and application practices in digital channels, but leaves several unresolved issues. First, there is a

lack of work that systematically describes the integration of neuromarketing into brand trust strategy in the digital environment. Second, there are discrepancies in the conclusions regarding the priority of emotional or cognitive triggers for the formation of consumer brand loyalty. Third, the relationship between personalization of communications, building trust, and sustainable brand development is insufficiently studied. These “blank spots” determine the scientific novelty of our research and justify the need for further interdisciplinary research.

Formulation of the article’s objectives (task statement). The article aims to explore ways to integrate neuromarketing into brand trust-building strategies in the digital environment, thereby enhancing the competitiveness of enterprises. To achieve the goal, the following research tasks have been defined:

1. To investigate modern scientific approaches to the use of neuromarketing technologies in the formation of consumer brand trust in the digital economy.
2. Analyze the possibilities of combining emotional-cognitive triggers and digital communication channels to create long-term trusting relationships between the brand and consumers.
3. Develop recommendations for enterprises on developing comprehensive strategies for integrating neuromarketing into brand reputation management, taking into account international experience and Ukrainian market realities.

Presentation of the main material of the study. The formation of trusting relationships with consumers in the digital age is increasingly based on the use of research results on the brain and behavioral reactions of a person. Neuromarketing, as an interdisciplinary field, combines neurobiology, psychology, and marketing to provide a deeper understanding of the unconscious factors influencing consumer choices [6, p. 208–209]. It is worth noting that up to 95% of consumer decisions are made subconsciously [17], so classic marketing methods focused only on conscious preferences often lose their effectiveness. Instead, neuromarketing introduces innovative neurotechnologies (from electroencephalography (EEG) to eye tracking) to record sincere emotional reactions to brand stimuli and adapt communications

accordingly. Due to this, marketers can form scientifically based strategies that enhance audience emotional engagement and content personalization.

The introduction of neurotechnologies enhances the effectiveness of communication with the target audience, enabling the creation of targeted marketing strategies and fostering a deeper emotional connection with consumers [1, p. 85-86]. It establishes a foundation for trust, as the brand demonstrates a profound understanding of the customers' needs and emotions. Modern content marketing is actively moving from a purely rational presentation of information to emotionally oriented formats that resonate with the consumers subconscious. Providing the audience with valuable and relevant content builds trust, authority and brand recognition. In conditions of information overload, consumers are looking for brands that speak to them in the language of their values and emotions – and neuromarketing approaches are designed to provide tools for this.

Global trends confirm the effectiveness of such integration of neuroscience into marketing. According to experts from Kyiv-Mohyla Business School (KMBS) [17], the global neuromarketing market reached \$1.57 billion in 2023 and is projected to grow to \$3.56 billion by 2032, which indicates business interest in these technologies.

In the post-pandemic world, there is a growing need for sustainable, mutually beneficial brand-customer relationships, which are recognized as a key source of competitive advantage. Modern neuromarketing strategies should support just such long-term interaction [8, p. 270-272]. At the same time, international studies demonstrate the increasing effectiveness of neuromarketing in the digital environment, generalizing specific applied approaches (from combining functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and electroencephalography (EEG) to the use of implicit associative tests) for its implementation [7, p. 38-39]. It confirms that a scientific approach to consumer psychology can yield measurable positive results for brands.

Modern scientific works outline the concept according to which neuromarketing technologies bring the development of brand strategies to a qualitatively new level. Using neurotools, a company can create a strong, positive image of the brand in the buyers mind, which activates an emotional response and thereby influences rational perception. As a result, a positive brand image through emotional associations makes it easier for consumers to decide in its favor. A. Danyliuk notes [6, p. 208-210] that most consumers associate brands with certain emotions and mental images; if these associations are positive, trust and loyalty are formed, if not, the impression of the brand can be spoiled.

Thus, modern scientists agree that the emotional component is critical for trust: neuromarketing allows you to measure and shape this component accurately, integrating the results into marketing decisions. The ability of a brand to speak the language of the consumers brain becomes a new marker of its customer orientation and reliability. Table 1 summarizes the primary neuromarketing methods, describes their purpose and impact on the formation of brand trust.

Table 1

Neuromarketing methods and their role in the formation of consumer trust

Method	Brief description and purpose	Potential for building trust (example of application)
Functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI)	Tracks changes in blood flow in the brain in response to stimuli, revealing the activation of emotional centers	Allows you to find out which images or messages evoke positive emotions in the consumers, which contributes to the formation of brand loyalty
Electroencephalography (EEG)	Records the electrical activity of the brain, reflecting engagement and attention	Helps identify moments in advertising communication that attract attention and inspire trust (for example, a calm tone of voice in advertising can reduce alertness)
Eye-tracking	Records which elements of the screen or advertisement a person looks at, and for how long	Identifies the most eye-catching elements (logo, slogan, facial image), which allows you to optimize the design for trust signals (for example, emphasize the characters eye contact with consumers)
Biometric indicators (pulse, etc.)	Measure unconscious physiological reactions:	Evaluate the level of emotional arousal from the content. A moderate increase

Method	Brief description and purpose	Potential for building trust (example of application)
	heart rate, sweating, breathing during interaction with a stimulus	in pulse or skin conductance when viewing an advertisement for a trusted brand may indicate excitement associated with trust and admiration, while a sharp jump indicates stress or distrust
Implicit associative tests, neutral-stimulus-based surveys	Psychological methods for identifying hidden associations and consumer attitudes towards brands	Allows for the identification of hidden preferences and stereotypes. For example, an implicit test can show that a brand is associated in the mind with «reliability», even if respondents do not articulate this directly - such an association is the basis for trust

Source: summarized based on [1, p. 85-86; 6, p. 208-210; 7, p. 38-39; 8, p. 270-272; 17]

The application of the methods presented in Table 1 allows brands to understand the psychophysiological reactions of consumers more deeply, which contributes to the objectification of trust: instead of assumptions about the impact of an advertising message, the company receives clear biometric indicators of the audiences emotional response. If, for example, using EEG and eye tracking, it is established that a particular video clip causes high attention and positive arousal in the target group without signs of stress, this indicates the formation of an emotional connection with the brand, that is, the emergence of trust. The scientific approach to measuring trust thus complements traditional marketing research (surveys, focus groups, etc.), reducing the subjectivity of assessments. As a result, companies will be able to make informed decisions regarding content and communications that increase competitiveness through deeper customer loyalty. To build long-term, trusting relationships with the target audience, it is not enough to have neuromarketing tools; it is necessary to integrate emotional triggers into the context of modern digital communication channels. The most significant effect is achieved precisely with the synergy of emotional and cognitive factors: brand messages should simultaneously evoke a positive emotional response and meet consumers rational expectations regarding quality, transparency, and brand values.

In the scientific literature, there is an ongoing discussion about the relative role of emotional and cognitive triggers in the formation of loyalty. In particular, some works emphasize the priority of emotional factors. For example, K. Shahzad and co-authors, based on their analysis, concluded that emotional stimuli associated with the fear of missing out on a profitable opportunity (FOMO), such as limited-time offers or exclusive offers, can significantly increase impulsive purchases, especially among consumers with a high tendency to impulsivity [4, p. 571–572]. It has been found that triggers such as limited-time offers or exclusive offers activate the emotion of urgency, which, with the participation of corresponding personal inclinations, is transformed into an action, such as making a purchase, subscribing, or recommending. Thus, in the digital environment, emotional triggers can directly influence behavior, bypassing long-term reflections, and this creates the prerequisites for the emergence of spontaneous trust («this brand understands me, it suits me»).

On the other hand, other researchers note that cognitive triggers - i.e., consciously perceived factors, such as the reliability of information, brand expertise, and reviews from other customers - are equally crucial for forming long-term loyalty. Thus, in conditions of information overload, the consumer values the relevance and content of messages [12]. The excess of content in digital channels leads to the fact that the audience develops «filters» against information noise. If the brand offers irrelevant or dubious information, the consumers protective mechanisms immediately increase distrust. Thus, an essential cognitive aspect of trust is the brands ability to provide helpful, truthful, and timely content.

International experience also confirms this thesis: consumers in mature markets (USA, Western Europe) increasingly demand transparency, ethics, and social responsibility from brands [10]. If the emotional component attracts the client, then the rational component retains him, providing intellectual justification for trust («I trust this brand because it is open and keeps its promises»). It is the combination

of emotional impulse with rational confirmation that forms a solid foundation for relationships.

Thus, to establish long-term trust, brands must work simultaneously on two levels: the emotional (unconscious) and cognitive (conscious) levels. At the emotional level, neuromarketing techniques for generating experiences are used – creating an exciting experience, using images that evoke warm feelings, and associating the brand with positive emotions. For example, the introduction of virtual or augmented reality elements into marketing opens up new opportunities for emotional interaction. D. Verzhykovskiy demonstrated that augmented reality technologies can significantly enhance the emotional experience of contact with a brand, especially in the luxury segment, where it is essential to immerse the consumer in the brand world [13]. Users, interacting with Augmented Reality content (AR content) (for example, virtually «trying on» products using AR or engaging with branded AR games), experience vivid emotions of surprise, joy, and delight – and these emotions are transferred to the brand, strengthening trust in it through the mechanism of pleasant associations.

At the cognitive level, companies should ensure the consistency and honesty of communications in digital channels. It is about ensuring that consumers receive consistent signals across all touchpoints (website, social media, email, messengers) that confirm brand trustworthiness. All of these trends aim to make interactions with consumers more intimate, holistic, and emotionally resonant, which ultimately translates into higher levels of trust (table 2).

Table 2

Current trends in digital communications for building brand trust

Trend	Characteristics and connection with consumer trust
Personalization	Adaptation of content and offers to individual customer needs. Increases trust, because consumers feel that attention to their preferences and values
Omnichannel	A consistent brand presence across all digital channels (website, social networks, applications, etc.). Ensures consistency of messages and service, which strengthens the sense of reliability: wherever the

Trend	Characteristics and connection with consumer trust
	customer encounters the brand, they receive an equally positive experience
Content visualization	Emphasis on visual forms of presentation (video, infographics, AR effects). Bright images more easily attract attention and have an emotional impact, forming lasting associations. For example, corporate identity and brand image in the mass media can inspire trust through recognition
Emotional storytelling	Integrating emotional stories (inspiration, nostalgia, humor) into the message. Helps establish an emotional connection: when a brand tells a story that resonates with consumers, the effect of empathy and trust arises
Analytics and adaptability	Using data (Big Data, neuroanalytics) for flexible real-time strategy changes. Monitoring audience reactions and quickly correcting errors (for example, adverse reaction to a campaign) demonstrates transparency and the brands willingness to take into account customer opinions, which strengthens trust

Source: summarized based on [4, p. 571-572; 10; 11, p. 64-66; 12; 13; 17]

Modern digital practices increasingly rely on taking into account the human factor (emotions, perception, individual experience) along with technological innovations. It is especially worth noting the role of visual images in the communication of trust, since they can influence the formation of a recognizable visual style through color schemes, images of heroes, and logos, which can evoke stable associations in memory and subconsciously increase the level of trust in the brand [9, p. 170-172]. That is, to create a holistic brand image in the digital space: from the design of the site to the style of posts in social networks, which evokes a sense of familiarity and comfort in the consumer. Another critical point is emotional content. It has been proven that emotional marketing (appeal to the feelings of consumers) can form unique competitive advantages for the brand [16, p. 335-337]. Emotional campaigns are more memorable and more likely to lead to repeat engagement, thereby creating the foundation for long-term loyalty. However, it is essential to remember that emotions alone are not enough – without support at the level of product quality and rational factors, the emotional effect can be short-lived. It is consistent with the general idea of the need for balance: emotional triggers of trust (e.g., evoking joy, a sense of security, or belonging to a community) should be reinforced by cognitive triggers (e.g., providing evidence of reliability – genuine

customer reviews, quality certificates, transparent terms of the deal). Strategically, brands should build an ecosystem of trust: each digital channel plays its role, but together they create a single positive experience. For example, a company website can serve as a source of comprehensive and truthful information (rational trust). At the same time, an Instagram page can demonstrate the «human face» of the brand through emotional customer success stories or behind-the-scenes videos (emotional trust). In parallel, personalized emails address the client by name and offer exactly those solutions that meet his needs, which combines both emotional (it is nice to get attention) and rational (usefulness) aspects. As a result, provided that such communications are consistent, a long-term relationship is formed: the consumer begins to perceive the brand as an understandable partner who can be trusted. Thus, the combination of emotional-cognitive triggers with the capabilities of digital channels opens the way to sustainable trust that stands the test of time and information noise. Based on the analysis, practical recommendations were formulated for companies seeking to develop a comprehensive strategy for integrating neuromarketing into brand management and reputation. These recommendations take into account both leading international experience and the specific needs of the Ukrainian market, which is currently undergoing digital transformation (table 3).

Table 3

Recommendations for integrating neuromarketing into brand trust strategies

Direction	Description
Implementation of ethical standards for neuromarketing	It is necessary to ensure transparency in the collection and use of consumer data. It will prevent possible ethical conflicts and maintain trust: the consumers should know that their neurodata will not be used to their detriment. In the context of growing demand for ethics, a brand that openly declares and adheres to the ethical norms of neuromarketing research will have an advantage in the audiences trust
Development of neuromarketing competencies	It is essential to invest in training marketing teams in the basics of neuropsychology and working with neurodata. Interdisciplinary cooperation (involving neurophysiologists and data analysts) will help to correctly interpret the results of neuromarketing research and implement them in strategies

Direction	Description
Personalization of interaction based on neuroinsights	It is essential to utilize the findings of neuromarketing research for more precise audience segmentation and targeting. The use of models based on artificial intelligence to build behavioral profiles will allow you to customize content for specific psychological types of consumers. It will increase the relevance of communications and the likelihood of a trusting response, especially in the Ukrainian market, where consumers value an individual approach after years of mass marketing
Adaptation of best international practices with consideration of local specifics	It is imperative to study the experiences of market leaders (USA, EU) in the application of neuromarketing (for example, successful emotional campaigns or the use of virtual reality technologies) and implement them, taking into account the cultural context and behavioral characteristics of Ukrainian consumers. It is recommended to conduct local pilot studies (focus groups, neurotests) to calibrate the methods
Data-based measurement of trust and effectiveness	Set clear trust KPIs (loyalty level, repeat purchases, etc.) and track their dynamics when implementing neuromarketing initiatives. Apply innovative analytical tools (Big Data, predictive analytics, etc.) to predict consumer behavior and early detect signals of loss of trust

Source: author's development

Therefore, integrating neuromarketing into brand trust-building strategies is a multi-stage task that requires both innovation and responsibility. Modern scientific approaches provide businesses with unique tools to peer into the consumers mind, the digital environment opens channels for constant dialogue, and the experience of world leaders and local experiments suggests how to move effectively and ethically. By following the above recommendations, Ukrainian brands will be able to build sustainable, trusting relationships with their customers – capital, the value of which outweighs any opportunistic benefits of short-term promotions and will ensure increased competitiveness of enterprises in the dynamic digital market, laying the foundation for their long-term success.

Conclusions. The issue of combining neuromarketing and brand trust-building strategies has acquired particular importance in the digital economy. The constant interaction of consumers with online content, high competition and the growing role of emotions in the choice of goods and services necessitate a deep

scientific understanding of new tools for influencing customer behavior. The study's results confirmed that neuromarketing opens up opportunities for accurately identifying unconscious motives and facilitates the transition from intuitive marketing to scientifically based trust management strategies.

The theoretical and methodological principles of using neuromarketing technologies have been studied, demonstrating their ability to detect consumers emotional reactions and establish stable trust relationships. The interaction of emotional and cognitive triggers with digital communication channels has been analyzed, enabling brands to integrate the unconscious and rational levels of perception into a holistic system of trust. The developed recommendations enable the comprehensive implementation of neuromarketing technologies, taking into account international experience and Ukrainian market realities, thereby creating the basis for a long-term partnership between the brand and the consumer.

The scientific novelty of the results obtained lies in the justification of an integrated strategy that combines neuroanalytics, digital communications and ethical standards for working with data. The practical value lies in the possibility of enterprises in various industries utilizing the proposed recommendations to develop marketing campaigns, prepare communication strategies, establish trust assessment systems, and predict customer behavior in real-time.

Further research should be directed towards the development of tools for quantitatively measuring the level of brand trust based on a combination of neurophysiological indicators and behavioral analytics. It is also promising to deepen the interdisciplinary approach, particularly by integrating artificial intelligence for the operational use of neurodata in personalized communication strategies. Such areas will enable the prediction of consumer behavior with even greater accuracy, ensuring the sustainable competitiveness of brands in a rapidly evolving digital environment.

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